

Supplementary Table S1. Detailed solute concentrations and isotopic compositions of sulfate for different water samples.

	Latitude / Longitude	low water / high water	T (oC)	pH	sediment concentration (g/L)	Solute concentrations (µM)										DIC (mM)	δD ₂ O	δ ¹⁸ O ₂	δ ³⁴ S _{SO4}	δ ¹⁸ O _{SO4}
						Ca	Mg	Sr	Na	Cs	Cl	SO ₄ ²⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻					
HLBS-w-112216	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	13.9	8.3	0.011	2028	47	3.12	88	BDL	12.6	0.95	2.07	-88.1	-15.05	NA	NA			
HLBS-w-122116	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	13.3	8.3	0.004	2163	97	3.14	107	BDL	BDL	1.01	1.35	-89.9	-13.07	2.0	-6.3			
HLBS-w-011217	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	10.9	8.5	NA	2290	101	3.23	117	BDL	6.0	1.13	1.27	-90.6	-13.00	0.9	-6.1			
HLBS-w-030717	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	9.9	6.5	NA	2338	105	3.28	126	1.38	9.0	1.15	2.77	-86.0	-11.93	2.1	-6.8			
HLBS-w-041917	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	15.3	7.0	NA	2187	102	3.29	111	1.31	BDL	1.24	2.56	-84.3	-11.98	2.1	-6.7			
HLBS-w-052417	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	14.8	8.3	NA	2256	90	3.31	112	0.00	8.0	1.10	2.13	-86.8	-11.34	2.4	-3.9			
HLBS-w-072517	23.245°N / 120.997°E	high	16.5	8.3	NA	2148	92	3.04	107	0.99	6.3	0.96	1.02	-85.9	-11.62	1.9	-5.9			
HLBS-w-082117	23.245°N / 120.997°E	high	14.5	8.0	NA	2089	100	3.02	101	1.00	6.6	1.04	1.19	-86.4	-12.53	2.0	-5.7			
HLBS-w-092717	23.245°N / 120.997°E	high	14.9	NA	NA	2081	89	3.10	100	1.21	5.5	0.97	2.15	-86.5	-12.30	1.7	-6.4			
HLBS-w-112317	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	13.9	NA	NA	2093	90	2.97	102	1.08	9.2	0.93	2.66	-88.1	-13.36	1.8	-6.5			
HLBS-w-122017	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	11.7	8.3	NA	2086	91	3.05	102	0.95	5.3	0.99	1.82	-87.0	-12.73	2.0	-6.4			
HLBS-w-012318	23.245°N / 120.997°E	low	12.0	8.3	NA	2091	88	2.92	102	1.02	5.5	1.00	2.42	-83.4	-11.64	1.5	-7.3			
LD-w-092216	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	NA	NA	0.674	2070	223	4.84	128	BDL	9.0	1.34	1.97	-80.9	-11.71	NA	NA			
LD-w-100416	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	22.9	8.0	0.587	1920	202	4.39	115	BDL	10.0	1.26	1.34	-89.1	-13.29	NA	NA			
LD-w-102716	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	20.3	8.2	0.288	1806	195	4.38	119	1.02	15.6	1.25	1.38	-91.3	-13.20	NA	NA			
LD-w-112316	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	19.8	8.4	0.037	2295	268	6.21	178	0.00	11.7	1.50	2.03	-85.1	-14.79	NA	NA			
LD-w-122116	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	17.8	8.3	0.007	2296	269	6.46	214	9.42	12.8	1.57	1.36	-84.9	-12.38	-4.8	-0.7			
LD-w-011117	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	16.5	8.2	0.005	2441	282	6.78	265	BDL	12.0	1.81	1.27	-78.3	-11.76	-4.2	-0.7			
LD-w-030717	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	14.9	6.5	0.003	2530	281	7.21	310	4.16	13.0	1.83	1.31	-80.2	-11.21	-4.9	-0.9			
LD-w-041917	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	23.5	7.0	0.006	2229	247	7.36	207	BDL	BDL	1.71	2.01	-79.9	-11.24	-5.6	-2.7			
LD-w-052417	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	21.7	8.3	0.026	2003	194	5.60	153	BDL	8.0	1.28	1.73	-78.8	-11.00	-6.0	-2.6			
LD-w-062117	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	19.9	8.2	0.385	1707	163	4.09	98	0.49	13.2	1.09	1.11	-77.5	-11.03	-6.6	-3.3			
LD-w-072517	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	24.4	8.0	0.096	2126	237	5.92	192	3.21	9.7	1.41	0.87	-77.0	-11.22	-5.3	-1.6			
LD-w-082117	23.183°N / 121.019°E	high	21.3	8.0	0.018	2082	176	2.19	154	0.50	11.0	1.45	1.14	-82.3	-11.68	-5.3	-2.1			
LD-w-092717	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	23.6	8.2	0.039	1990	238	6.06	188	2.62	BDL	1.42	1.70	-81.9	-11.79	-5.2	-1.0			
LD-w-112317	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	18.9	NA	0.028	2275	265	6.51	194	2.79	9.8	1.50	2.47	-80.1	-12.35	-5.2	-0.8			
LD-w-122017	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	15.8	8.5	0.013	2314	260	6.59	214	2.81	10.4	1.58	1.41	-79.8	-11.86	-5.0	-0.9			
LD-w-012318	23.183°N / 121.019°E	low	16.4	8.2	0.008	2122	223	5.67	173	2.77	8.1	1.42	1.97	-87.1	-12.53	-6.1	-3.2			
MLL-w-092216	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	NA	NA	23.995	2941	618	5.75	144	BDL	BDL	2.78	NA	-82.2	-11.66	NA	NA			
MLL-w-100416	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	22.0	7.9	22.225	2530	476	4.56	119	BDL	16.0	2.36	NA	-83.6	-13.90	NA	NA			
MLL-w-102716	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	20.5	8.1	1.038	2515	471	5.27	107	0.57	27.1	2.13	NA	-90.4	-13.52	NA	NA			
MLL-w-112316	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	20.1	8.3	0.285	2979	611	7.17	129	BDL	16.5	2.47	NA	-84.6	-14.64	NA	NA			
MLL-w-122116	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	18.5	8.4	0.119	2995	602	7.33	142	7.06	76.0	2.52	NA	-84.3	-12.27	-4.5	2.4			
MLL-w-011117	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	16.4	8.3	0.051	3134	609	7.42	161	BDL	14.4	2.74	1.15	-82.9	-11.65	-3.9	2.2			
MLL01-w-030817	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	NA	7.8	NA	3591	700	8.55	150	1.38	24.0	3.40	1.41	-72.7	-10.67	-3.7	1.2			
MLL02-w-030817	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	NA	NA	1.724	2933	522	6.61	144	1.07	10.0	2.61	1.59	NA	NA	NA	NA			
MLL02-w-042017	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	21.0	7.3	0.115	2971	574	8.02	145	0.97	BDL	2.85	1.71	-78.2	-10.77	-3.6	1.5			
MLL02-w-052417	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	24.2	8.2	1.744	2590	455	6.21	122	BDL	BDL	2.20	1.04	-78.1	-10.97	-4.0	0.5			
MLL02-w-060617	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	21.8	8.3	7.943	2169	376	3.92	91	BDL	BDL	1.95	0.80	-76.0	-11.10	-6.9	-1.0			
MLL02-w-072517	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	NA	NA	0.087	2879	524	6.25	129	1.32	9.9	2.17	0.85	-76.5	-11.11	-3.7	1.6			
MLL02-w-082117	23.172°N / 121.035°E	high	21.6	8.1	0.024	2748	548	6.60	121	1.70	8.9	2.53	1.20	-82.4	-11.79	-4.7	2.3			
MLL02-w-092617	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	24.2	7.9	0.083	2750	559	6.94	134	1.45	BDL	2.30	1.67	-81.6	-11.55	-4.1	1.7			
MLL02-w-112217	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	19.6	NA	0.133	2940	587	7.14	137	1.14	9.0	2.37	2.47	-80.7	-12.06	-3.9	1.6			
MLL02-w-121917	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	15.9	8.6	0.130	2954	571	7.03	134	1.19	9.2	2.42	1.87	-81.2	-11.93	-4.3	2.0			
MLL02-w-012218	23.172°N / 121.035°E	low	18.4	8.5	0.162	2878	527	6.53	128	0.75	8.7	2.36	1.97	-80.3	-11.63	-4.6	0.5			
CWL01-w-092216	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	NA	NA	4.861	1846	388	4.08	215	BDL	26.2	1.29	1.41	-86.1	-12.65	NA	NA			
CWL01-w-100416	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	22.7	7.9	5.952	1730	339	3.76	173	BDL	20.4	1.24	1.84	-89.9	-13.82	NA	NA			
CWL01-w-102716	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	21.7	7.8	1.977	1815	327	4.23	203	0.18	35.0	1.29	1.37	-93.5	-13.62	NA	NA			
CWL01-w-112316	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	21.8	8.3	0.104	2083	408	5.48	284	BDL	27.4	1.43	1.50	-86.3	-14.91	NA	NA			
CWL01-w-122016	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	19.7	8.3	0.023	2102	433	5.74	372	20.13	30.1	1.41	1.31	-85.7	-12.16	-5.2	0.3			
CWL01-w-011017	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	18.3	8.3	0.011	2138	436	5.89	473	0.00	34.0	1.49	NA	-86.0	-12.33	-5.3	1.3			
CWL01-w-030717	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	16.9	8.0	0.004	2160	429	6.18	598	20.65	42.0	1.68	1.74	-85.3	-11.57	-5.0	1.6			
CWL01-w-041817	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	25.2	7.7	0.025	1963	350	6.41	426	18.45	33.8	1.66	1.66	-81.1	-11.60	-5.8	1.4			
CWL01-w-052317	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	25.0	8.3	0.486	1885	280	5.29	298	BDL	21.0	1.31	1.96	-86.1	-11.43	-5.2	1.0			
CWL01-w-060617	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	22.6	8.1	13.721	1459	227	2.93	146	BDL	13.0	1.51	1.23	-80.2	-11.73	-6.2	-3.3			
CWL01-w-062017	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	19.8	8.1	6.177	1575	228	3.44	162	0.39	17.3	0.97	0.98	-82.2	-11.80	-5.9	-2.5			
CWL01-w-072417	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	25.7	8.1	0.138	1553	368	5.16	348	8.75	30.2	1.40	0.91	-79.7	-12.24	-4.5	0.8			
CWL01-w-082017	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	26.2	8.1	0.062	1766	365	4.97	285	6.92	24.0	1.32	1.38	-84.6	-12.00	-4.6	-0.1			
CWL01-w-092617	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	26.6	8.2	0.047	1758	374	5.23	321	9.96	27.5	1.32	1.86	-85.5	-12.22	-4.5	0.7			
CWL01-w-101817	23.134°N / 121.119°E	high	21.2	7.9	6.592	1668	344	3.57	180	0.44	23.0	1.05	2.06	-89.2	-11.99	-6.2	-1.6			
CWL01-w-112217	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	NA	NA	0.234	2006	419	5.54	323	10.20	28.3	1.37	2.62	-85.1	-12.34	-4.8	0.9			
CWL01-w-122017	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	18.4	8.5	0.053	2004	392	5.58	362	12.21	30.5	1.37	1.75	-84.3	-12.41	-4.7	1.3			
CWL01-w-012318	23.134°N / 121.119°E	low	18.8	8.3	0.016	1981	349	5.26	345	11.18	26.5	1.44	2.33	-83.0	-12.24	-5.5	-1.3			
DL-w-092216	23.133°N / 121.119°E	high	NA	NA	1.008	1329	169	2.44	227	0.00	57.5	0.70	1.41	-83.4	-12.69	NA	NA			
DL-w-100416	23.133°N / 121.119°E	high	21.3	7.9	2.785	1159	149	2.11	188	0.00	46.9	0.66	1.38	-86.8	-14.02	NA	NA			
DL-w-102716-09	23.133°N / 121.119°E	high	20.6	8.1	0.709	1169	142	2.22	213	15.75	138.0	0.64	1.78	-89.6	-14.19	NA	NA			
DL-w-102716-14	23.133°N / 121.119°E	high	NA	NA	NA	1179	145	2.23	224	2.73	61.4	0.64	NA	-94.6	-13.87	NA	NA			

Spring				Ca(μM)	Mg(μM)	Sr(μM)	Na(μM)	Cs(nM)	Cl (μM)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mM)	DIC (mM)	δD_H2O	δ18O_H2O	δ34S_SO4	δ18O_SO4
LS01-spr-030817	23.224°N / 120.813°E	-	52.0 8.1	1051	443.7	12.12	10905	712	140	0.61	12.6	-93.0	-12.69	7.7	1.2
LK-spr-030717	23.175°N / 121.030°E	-	93.9 6.6	73	14.8	9.31	11706	636	607	0.39	13.4	-83.1	-11.19	NA	NA
LK-spr-072517	23.175°N / 121.030°E	-	NA NA	129	12.5	8.17	12747	594	568	0.15	15.5	-77.7	-10.73	NA	NA
WL-spr-030717	23.174°N / 121.042°E	-	40.9 6.6	59	7.4	3.70	12468	474	286	0.87	11.9	-83.5	-11.49	52.3	6.7
LL01-spr-030817	23.124°N / 121.053°E	-	89.0 9.1	27	44.0	2.70	25537	3784	12844	1.87	16.3	-76.0	-8.48	14.2	-3.1
LL02-spr-030817	23.124°N / 121.050°E	-	86.5 9.1	18	18.2	0.72	21465	3316	10366	1.48	15.6	-73.3	-8.19	14.5	0.2
Groundwater				Ca(μM)	Mg(μM)	Sr(μM)	Na(μM)	Cs(nM)	Cl (μM)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mM)	DIC (mM)	δD_H2O	δ18O_H2O	δ34S_SO4	δ18O_SO4
DL-BH02-67m-W-091218	23.131°N / 121.117°E	-	NA 7.74	3504	594	63.6	7498	55	1328	9.19	3.30	-74.8	-10.66	38.8	11.5
DL-BH02-67m-W-101518	23.131°N / 121.117°E	-	NA 7.54	2399	408	46.4	4187	42	787	6.03	3.16	-63.6	-9.45	38.5	11.5
DL-BH02-85m-W-101518	23.131°N / 121.117°E	-	NA 7.43	1778	285	30.9	4152	26	360	4.01	1.24	-55.8	-8.37	36.6	10.0
Rain				Ca(μM)	Mg(μM)	Sr(μM)	Na(μM)	Cs(nM)	Cl (μM)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (μM)	DIC (mM)	δD_H2O	δ18O_H2O	δ34S_SO4	δ18O_SO4
LD-rw-072517	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	23.2	12.5	0.35	9.1	0.15	17.8	21.0	0.22	-37.2	-5.73	NA	NA
LD-rw-072617	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	23.7	8.8	0.52	2.8	0.10	5.9	6.5	0.13	-29.4	-4.56	NA	NA
LD-rw-072717	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	15.0	11.0	0.21	4.8	0.23	14.2	12.9	0.05	-17.3	-3.62	NA	NA
LD-rw-073117	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	23.5	11.5	0.36	3.5	0.05	14.4	9.6	0.24	-77.6	-8.86	NA	NA
LD-rw-010418	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	26.7	26.1	0.45	13.8	BDL	25.6	31.9	0.17	-17.8	-4.74	NA	NA
LD-rw-010518	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	11.6	2.2	0.15	1.4	BDL	3.6	2.3	0.08	-24.2	-5.25	NA	NA
LD-rw-010718	23.187°N / 121.025°E	-	- NA	9.0	6.4	0.10	1.2	BDL	5.6	7.4	0.09	-40.2	-6.88	NA	NA

"NA": not available/no analysis

"-": no this type of data

"BDL": below detection limit

Supplementary Table S2. Sampling information and alpha diversity indices of the analyzed samples based on the rarefied dataset of 16S rRNA amplicons (n = 4,899).

Sample name	Site	Latitude / Longitude	Date	Type	low water/ high water	Observed species	Chao1	se.chao1	ACE	se.ACE	Shannon
CWL01_w_091216	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.12	Water	high	231	251.04	9.08	247.77	7.15	4.03
CWL01_w_092216	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.22	Water	high	402	500.72	23.34	508.19	10.91	3.97
CWL01_w_100416	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.04	Water	high	180	193.59	6.68	198.07	6.56	3.29
CWL01_w_102716	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.27	Water	high	450	571.63	27.02	573.01	11.70	4.59
CWL01_w_011017	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.01.10	Water	low	816	890.54	16.33	898.97	12.43	6.27
CWL01_w_030717	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.03.07	Water	low	1252	1675.41	51.01	1733.76	21.71	6.43
CWL01_w_052317	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.05.23	Water	low	499	557.72	15.37	556.66	9.90	4.94
CWL01_s_060617	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.06	SED	high	181	298.43	38.03	263.95	8.65	2.42
CWL01_w_060617	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.06	Water	high	132	137.69	4.19	138.48	5.61	2.80
CWL01_w_062017	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.20	Water	high	412	781.58	70.63	812.60	17.31	3.71
CWL01_w_092617	CWL01	23.134°N / 121.119°E	2017.09.26	Water	low	722	811.45	19.00	821.63	12.65	5.84
CWL04_w_091216	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2016.09.12	Water	high	501	569.83	16.60	585.45	10.85	4.90
CWL04_w_092216	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2016.09.22	Water	high	149	156.50	5.23	155.79	6.10	3.64
CWL04_w_100416	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2016.10.04	Water	high	211	248.60	14.26	242.97	7.16	3.43
CWL04_w_102716	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2016.10.27	Water	high	393	484.98	23.99	470.64	10.12	4.58
CWL04_w_011017	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.01.10	Water	low	717	793.99	17.32	794.13	11.51	5.86
CWL04_w_030817	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.03.08	Water	low	643	695.81	14.09	690.85	10.93	5.77
CWL04_w_052417	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.05.24	Water	low	590	636.06	12.51	640.09	10.81	5.64
CWL04_w_060617	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.06.06	Water	high	205	234.22	11.22	238.34	7.17	2.96
CWL04_s_060617	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.06.06	SED	high	360	477.25	26.63	498.48	11.70	3.65
CWL04_w_062017	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.06.20	Water	high	183	199.24	8.76	193.88	6.34	3.51
CWL04_w_092717	CWL04	23.127°N / 121.171°E	2017.09.27	Water	low	338	347.50	5.73	344.48	9.00	5.18
DL_w_091216	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.12	Water	high	731	793.79	15.63	783.91	11.21	6.05
DL_s_091216	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.12	SED	high	371	393.56	8.71	394.34	9.09	4.99
DL_w_092216	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.22	Water	high	369	424.78	15.87	434.75	9.76	4.51
DL_s_092216	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.09.22	SED	high	273	326.63	16.46	335.08	9.00	3.84
DL_w_100416	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.04	Water	high	278	301.52	8.97	307.43	7.91	4.18
DL_s_100416	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.04	SED	high	199	224.16	10.48	225.82	7.10	3.70
DL_w_102716	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.27	Water	high	386	422.62	11.07	438.12	9.36	4.62
DL_s_102716	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2016.10.27	SED	high	207	234.79	12.76	223.89	7.01	4.02
DL_w_011017	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.01.10	Water	low	694	776.94	19.21	763.91	11.77	5.95
DL_s_011017	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.01.10	SED	low	487	536.69	14.68	530.32	10.39	5.34
DL_w_030717	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.03.07	Water	low	789	988.15	32.13	1015.06	15.15	4.94
DL_s_030717	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.03.07	SED	low	646	689.06	11.44	699.62	10.66	5.38
DL_w_052317	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.05.23	Water	low	1149	1500.12	46.25	1511.52	19.39	6.37
DL_s_052417	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.05.24	SED	low	442	469.82	11.04	458.46	9.88	5.56
DL_w_060617	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.06	Water	high	181	187.77	4.17	190.91	6.01	3.00
DL_s_060617	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.06	SED	high	449	646.40	38.14	671.28	14.45	3.52
DL_w_062017	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.20	Water	high	196	216.78	9.41	217.20	7.00	3.62
DL_s_062017	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.06.20	SED	high	188	200.04	6.36	201.30	6.64	3.70
DL_w_092617	DL	23.133°N / 121.119°E	2017.09.26	Water	low	910	1165.32	38.96	1183.41	17.04	6.05
LD_w_091216	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2016.09.12	Water	high	506	523.22	6.65	527.48	9.54	5.46
LD_w_092216	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2016.09.22	Water	high	392	406.44	6.30	408.05	9.00	5.10
LD_w_100416	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2016.10.04	Water	high	444	491.75	13.73	492.35	9.62	4.99
LD_w_102716	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2016.10.27	Water	high	717	868.21	27.50	881.13	13.83	5.56
LD_w_011117	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2017.01.11	Water	low	906	992.68	17.78	994.01	12.22	6.39
LD_w_030717	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2017.03.07	Water	low	1087	1344.31	36.02	1376.59	17.21	6.04
LD_w_052417	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2017.05.24	Water	low	905	1036.82	24.28	1028.43	13.45	6.33
LD_w_062117	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2017.06.21	Water	high	358	379.02	8.47	378.60	8.97	4.89
LD_w_092617	LD	23.183°N / 121.019°E	2017.09.26	Water	low	262	262.08	0.34	262.41	8.02	4.98
LK_spr_030717	LK	23.175°N / 121.030°E	2017.03.07	SPR	NA	839	996.56	26.84	1011.43	13.87	5.63
LL01_spr_030817	LL01	23.124°N / 121.053°E	2017.03.08	SPR	NA	445	575.10	26.88	605.02	12.98	3.84
LL02_spr_030817	LL02	23.124°N / 121.050°E	2017.03.08	SPR	NA	354	417.80	17.82	416.56	9.20	3.63
LS01_spr_030817	LS01	23.224°N / 120.813°E	2017.03.08	SPR	NA	1001	1626.14	76.20	1778.59	26.79	5.64
MLL_w_011117	MLL	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.01.11	Water	low	1460	2305.60	83.53	2567.34	32.70	6.46
MLL_w_091216	MLL	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2016.09.12	Water	high	191	211.52	9.17	214.26	6.85	3.07
MLL_w_092216	MLL	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2016.09.22	Water	high	210	213.25	2.68	214.42	7.06	3.68
MLL_w_100416	MLL	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2016.10.04	Water	high	199	231.23	12.23	235.24	7.09	2.81
MLL_w_102716	MLL	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2016.10.27	Water	high	270	286.84	7.28	290.40	7.82	4.13
MLL02_s_060617	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.06.06	SED	high	696	750.15	14.11	745.53	11.48	6.04
MLL02_w_030817	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.03.08	Water	low	950	1207.56	38.69	1200.27	16.36	6.05
MLL02_w_052417	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.05.24	Water	low	392	492.01	23.26	504.61	11.22	3.89
MLL02_w_060617	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.06.06	Water	high	127	134.00	5.06	133.06	5.26	2.48
MLL02_w_062117	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.06.21	Water	high	281	340.08	16.90	362.62	9.83	3.18
MLL02_w_092617	MLL02	23.172°N / 121.035°E	2017.09.26	Water	low	792	953.31	27.59	982.94	14.57	5.53
SCIH_01_soil_011117	SCIH_01	23.133°N / 121.144°E	2017.01.11	Soil	NA	1488	1848.76	42.88	1868.13	19.87	6.94
SCIH_03_soil_011117	SCIH_03	23.134°N / 121.122°E	2017.01.11	Soil	NA	675	693.01	6.62	695.54	10.53	6.09
SCIH_03_soil_122016	SCIH_03	23.142°N / 121.100°E	2016.12.20	Soil	NA	811	854.48	11.41	857.53	11.45	6.32
SCIH_04_schist_011117	SCIH_04	23.160°N / 121.049°E	2017.01.11	Schist	NA	527	555.84	9.43	558.08	10.03	5.40
SCIH_05_schist_011117	SCIH_05	23.180°N / 121.024°E	2017.01.11	Schist	NA	262	265.47	2.91	265.34	7.73	4.50

SCIH_05_soil_122116	SCIH_05	23.240°N / 121.003°E	2016.12.21	Soil	NA	1377	1799.57	48.84	1865.23	21.78	6.58
SCIH_06_soil_122116	SCIH_06	23.245°N / 120.997°E	2016.12.21	Soil	NA	513	523.16	5.46	519.79	10.45	5.95
SCIH_10_soil_011217	SCIH_10	23.245°N / 120.997°E	2017.01.12	Soil	NA	1491	1936.66	49.72	1993.43	22.70	6.81
SH07_sw_011217	SH07	23.240°N / 121.003°E	2017.01.12	SW	NA	431	486.12	14.88	490.30	9.28	4.25
SH16_sw_052417	SH16	23.240°N / 121.003°E	2017.05.24	SW	NA	1090	1254.28	26.08	1274.07	15.02	6.52
SH17_sw_052417	SH17	23.171°N / 121.036°E	2017.05.24	SW	NA	508	574.45	17.33	566.11	9.95	4.88
SH18_sw_052417	SH18	23.159°N / 121.050°E	2017.05.24	SW	NA	732	797.82	15.67	793.31	11.42	6.06
SH19_sw_052417	SH19	23.153°N / 121.065°E	2017.05.24	SW	NA	673	710.50	11.50	700.05	10.80	6.13
SM_spr_030817	SM	23.156°N / 121.062°E	2017.03.08	SPR	NA	760	1061.14	43.85	1151.39	19.79	5.15
WL_spr_030717	WL	23.173°N / 121.042°E	2017.03.07	SPR	NA	205	276.19	22.96	276.68	8.76	3.30
soil_38_052417	SH16	23.240°N / 121.003°E	2017.05.24	Soil	NA	624	646.10	8.27	641.19	10.96	6.10
soil_40_052417	SH18	23.160°N / 121.050°E	2017.05.24	Soil	NA	1000	1118.91	22.61	1094.80	12.00	6.53
DL_BH02_67m_W_101518	DL-BH02	23.131°N / 121.117°E	2018.10.15	GW	NA	589	645.29	15.34	633.75	10.50	5.64
DL_BH02_70m_W_091218	DL-BH02	23.131°N / 121.117°E	2018.09.12	GW	NA	403	425.97	8.50	428.01	9.14	4.86
DL_BH02_85m_W_101518	DL-BH02	23.131°N / 121.117°E	2018.10.15	GW	NA	610	663.23	14.07	660.72	10.82	5.67

1. Abbreviations for column names include "Chao1" for Chao1 richness estimator, "se.Chao1" for standard error of Chao1's estimator, "ACE" for abundance-based coverage estimator, "se.ACE" for standard error of abundance-based coverage estimator, and "Shannon" for Shannon–Wiener diversity index.

2. Abbreviations for sample types include "Water" for river water, "SED" for benthic sediment, "SPR" for hot spring, "SW" for short path creek, and "GW" for

Supplementary Table S3. Statistics of Dunn's multiple comparison test on alpha diversity indices between types of samples.

Comparison	Observed species		ACE		Shannon ¹	
	Z	p	Z	p	Z	p
Schist – SED ²	0.25	0.80	0.00	1.00	0.47	0.64
Schist - Soil	-1.79	0.07	-1.80	0.07	-1.86	0.06
SED ² - Soil	-3.51	0.00	-3.13	0.00	-4.02	0.00
Schist – SPR ²	-0.71	0.48	-1.10	0.27	0.32	0.75
SED ² - SPR ²	-1.54	0.12	-1.80	0.07	-0.20	0.84
Soil - SPR ²	1.54	0.12	0.97	0.33	3.22	0.00
Schist - SW ²	-1.10	0.27	-1.14	0.26	-0.86	0.39
SED ² - SW ²	-2.08	0.04	-1.80	0.07	-2.03	0.04
Soil - SW ²	0.87	0.38	0.83	0.41	1.33	0.18
SPR ² - SW ²	-0.56	0.58	-0.09	0.93	-1.62	0.11
Schist - Water	-0.28	0.78	-0.47	0.64	0.06	0.95
SED ² - Water	-1.21	0.23	-1.06	0.29	-0.99	0.32
Soil - Water	3.18	0.00	2.84	0.00	3.98	0.00
SPR ² - Water	0.88	0.38	1.29	0.20	-0.51	0.61
SW ² - Water	1.53	0.13	1.31	0.19	1.62	0.11
Schist - GW ²	-0.53	0.60	-0.54	0.59	-0.47	0.64
SED ² - GW ²	-1.04	0.30	-0.77	0.44	-1.22	0.22
Soil - GW ²	1.37	0.17	1.37	0.17	1.55	0.12
SPR ² - GW ²	0.14	0.89	0.57	0.57	-0.97	0.33
SW ² - GW ²	0.60	0.55	0.63	0.53	0.40	0.69
Water - GW ²	-0.47	0.64	-0.26	0.80	-0.79	0.43

1. Abbreviations of alpha diversity indices are the same as Supplementary Table S2.

2. Abbreviations for sample types include "Water" for river water, "SED" for benthic sediment, "SPR" for hot spring, "SW" for short path creek, and "GW" for groundwater.

Supplementary Table S4. Abundances of total bacteria, and *Sulfuricurvum* and *Thiobacillus* members based on qPCR analyses of 16S rRNA genes, and copies or amplicon proportions of either genus to the total bacteria

Sample name	Type	Bacteria (copies L ⁻¹ or g ⁻¹)	<i>Sulfuricurvum</i> (copies L ⁻¹ or g ⁻¹)	<i>Thiobacillus</i> (copies L ⁻¹ or g ⁻¹)	<i>Sulfuricurvum</i> copies proportion	<i>Thiobacillus</i> copies proportion	<i>Sulfuricurvum</i> amplicon proportion	<i>Thiobacillus</i> amplicon proportion
CWL01_s_060617	SED ¹	1.09E+06	5.23E+05	1.81E+05	48.1%	16.7%	73.8%	11.3%
CWL01_w_011017	Water ²	2.78E+07	1.31E+06	2.53E+06	4.7%	9.1%	0.2%	2.8%
CWL01_w_030717	Water ²	6.77E+05	0.00E+00	1.41E+04	0.0%	2.1%	0.4%	0.2%
CWL01_w_052317	Water ²	2.01E+07	4.48E+06	1.65E+07	22.3%	82.1%	21.7%	21.9%
CWL01_w_060617	Water ²	2.99E+07	1.77E+07	3.00E+06	59.2%	10.0%	71.6%	5.6%
CWL01_w_062017	Water ²	7.76E+08	2.98E+08	9.73E+07	38.4%	12.5%	50.3%	13.2%
CWL01_w_091216	Water ²	2.68E+07	7.09E+06	1.28E+07	26.5%	47.8%	27.7%	28.3%
CWL01_w_092216	Water ²	9.49E+07	1.21E+07	5.17E+06	12.8%	5.4%	49.3%	8.1%
CWL01_w_092717	Water ²	5.69E+05	8.54E+04	2.52E+04	15.0%	4.4%	0.8%	2.4%
CWL01_w_100416	Water ²	3.83E+08	1.66E+08	5.65E+07	43.3%	14.8%	56.0%	11.2%
CWL01_w_102716	Water ²	9.38E+07	3.01E+07	2.24E+07	32.1%	23.9%	29.7%	12.6%
CWL04_s_060617	SED ¹	2.63E+05	2.41E+04	3.71E+05	9.2%	141.4%	33.2%	18.5%
CWL04_w_011017	Water ²	3.12E+07	2.79E+05	1.50E+05	0.9%	0.5%	0.4%	0.3%
CWL04_w_030817	Water ²	1.59E+06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%
CWL04_w_052417	Water ²	6.82E+07	1.43E+06	1.57E+07	2.1%	23.0%	7.6%	10.8%
CWL04_w_060617	Water ²	7.44E+06	4.08E+06	3.92E+05	54.8%	5.3%	73.4%	4.7%
CWL04_w_062017	Water ²	1.32E+09	3.47E+08	1.18E+08	26.3%	8.9%	50.5%	13.0%
CWL04_w_091216	Water ²	6.31E+07	9.33E+06	5.66E+07	14.8%	89.7%	17.3%	23.1%
CWL04_w_092216	Water ²	1.91E+08	2.36E+07	1.56E+07	12.4%	8.2%	25.6%	35.5%
CWL04_w_092717	Water ²	6.78E+07	4.24E+05	4.44E+06	0.6%	6.5%	1.0%	4.2%
CWL04_w_100416	Water ²	2.29E+08	1.14E+08	2.76E+07	49.8%	12.1%	54.3%	13.1%
CWL04_w_102716	Water ²	6.54E+07	2.28E+07	4.06E+07	34.9%	62.1%	31.7%	14.1%
DL_s_011017	SED ¹	9.80E+06	3.93E+03	1.33E+06	0.0%	13.6%	0.6%	6.0%
DL_s_030717	SED ¹	2.09E+08	5.80E+04	8.84E+06	0.0%	4.2%	0.6%	1.4%
DL_s_052317	SED ¹	8.48E+07	1.80E+06	1.14E+07	2.1%	13.4%	3.9%	10.0%
DL_s_060617	SED ¹	1.45E+05	6.97E+04	9.29E+04	48.1%	64.1%	60.6%	12.4%
DL_s_062017	SED ¹	1.13E+06	3.00E+05	2.74E+05	26.6%	24.3%	42.1%	16.7%
DL_s_091216	SED ¹	9.34E+07	3.94E+06	2.73E+07	4.2%	29.2%	9.1%	15.1%
DL_s_092216	SED ¹	2.79E+06	4.89E+05	1.27E+06	17.5%	45.4%	43.1%	20.4%
DL_s_100416	SED ¹	9.78E+05	6.33E+05	8.12E+06	64.8%	829.9%	37.8%	22.7%
DL_s_102716	SED ¹	3.01E+07	2.10E+06	2.11E+08	7.0%	700.5%	23.4%	23.4%
DL_w_011017	Water ²	2.84E+07	3.59E+05	1.26E+06	1.3%	4.4%	1.7%	3.2%
DL_w_030717	Water ²	7.64E+05	6.57E+03	1.66E+04	0.9%	2.2%	0.2%	0.4%
DL_w_052317	Water ²	3.91E+07	6.75E+05	9.16E+06	1.7%	23.4%	1.8%	4.0%
DL_w_060617	Water ²	2.45E+07	1.64E+07	1.57E+06	66.9%	6.4%	71.8%	5.5%
DL_w_062017	Water ²	3.87E+08	1.08E+08	4.18E+07	27.9%	10.8%	48.1%	11.9%
DL_w_091216	Water ²	2.97E+07	3.84E+05	1.17E+07	1.3%	39.4%	1.6%	5.3%
DL_w_092216	Water ²	3.10E+07	7.01E+06	6.90E+06	22.6%	22.3%	25.9%	16.8%
DL_w_092617	Water ²	1.57E+07	6.24E+04	8.04E+05	0.4%	5.1%	0.3%	2.8%
DL_w_100416	Water ²	1.07E+08	3.62E+07	2.30E+07	33.8%	21.5%	38.3%	10.1%
DL_w_102716	Water ²	1.14E+08	3.57E+07	3.38E+07	31.3%	29.6%	29.2%	14.4%
LD_w_011017	Water ²	5.07E+06	1.59E+05	4.61E+04	3.1%	0.9%	2.2%	1.2%
LD_w_030717	Water ²	3.32E+05	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.2%
LD_w_052417	Water ²	6.77E+06	4.87E+04	7.83E+05	0.7%	11.6%	0.8%	2.2%
LD_w_062117	Water ²	1.32E+08	1.41E+07	1.30E+07	10.7%	9.8%	15.2%	9.3%
LD_w_091216	Water ²	3.18E+07	2.84E+06	5.34E+06	8.9%	16.8%	9.1%	11.6%
LD_w_092216	Water ²	9.18E+07	2.95E+06	6.71E+06	3.2%	7.3%	13.6%	7.8%
LD_w_092617	Water ²	3.01E+05	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	1.6%
LD_w_100416	Water ²	2.80E+07	4.59E+06	3.33E+06	16.4%	11.9%	12.3%	4.5%
LD_w_102716	Water ²	2.59E+07	1.91E+06	2.48E+06	7.4%	9.6%	6.7%	4.2%
LK_spr_030717	SPR ³	1.88E+06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.1%
LL01_spr_030817	SPR ³	4.69E+07	4.21E+03	8.45E+04	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.1%
LL02_spr_030817	SPR ³	5.66E+06	0.00E+00	9.13E+03	0.0%	0.2%	0.5%	0.3%
LS01_spr_030817	SPR ³	1.21E+07	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.7%

MLL_w_091216	Water ²	7.09E+07	1.10E+07	7.71E+06	15.5%	10.9%	65.0%	10.1%
MLL_w_092216	Water ²	2.35E+07	1.07E+07	7.29E+05	45.5%	3.1%	53.2%	5.8%
MLL_w_100416	Water ²	1.02E+08	9.36E+07	5.38E+06	91.8%	5.3%	72.9%	3.6%
MLL_w_102716	Water ²	6.32E+07	2.16E+07	5.75E+06	34.2%	9.1%	35.2%	7.2%
MLL_w_011117	Water ²	5.17E+07	3.14E+06	5.03E+06	6.1%	9.7%	1.6%	4.5%
MLL_w_030817	Water ²	5.16E+08	2.30E+07	1.16E+08	4.5%	22.5%	2.9%	7.7%
MLL_w_052417	Water ²	3.07E+07	3.37E+05	3.91E+06	1.1%	12.7%	40.4%	24.3%
MLL_w_060617	Water ²	8.35E+06	6.78E+06	3.63E+05	81.2%	4.3%	80.1%	4.1%
MLL_w_062117	Water ²	3.87E+08	1.48E+08	1.50E+07	38.2%	3.9%	65.1%	5.7%
MLL_w_092617	Water ²	4.60E+07	7.64E+05	2.46E+06	1.7%	5.3%	2.3%	2.7%
MLL02_s_060617	SED ¹	1.50E+07	3.12E+05	5.78E+05	2.1%	3.8%	3.6%	3.6%
SH07_sw_011217	SW ⁴	3.06E+07	1.01E+05	1.02E+04	0.3%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%
SH16_sw_052417	SW ⁴	1.26E+07	1.01E+04	1.47E+04	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%
SH17_sw_052417	SW ⁴	8.93E+06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	24.6%	18.9%
SH18_sw_052417	SW ⁴	3.29E+06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%
SH19_sw_052417	SW ⁴	1.00E+07	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%
SH31_sw_072517	SW ⁴	2.22E+07	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%
SM_spr_030817	SPR ³	1.33E+07	4.16E+04	8.38E+05	0.3%	6.3%	0.2%	0.6%
soil_38_052417	Soil ⁵	7.57E+08	2.06E+05	3.11E+05	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.5%
soil_40_052417	Soil ⁵	5.92E+08	1.20E+05	6.86E+04	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
WL_spr_030717	SPR ³	4.74E+07	4.55E+03	1.94E+04	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%

1. SED for benthic sediment. The 16S rRNA gene copies in this category are normalized to the wet weight (g) of the sample.

2. Water for river water. The 16S rRNA gene copies in this category are normalized to the volume (liter) of the sample.

3. SPR for hot spring. The 16S rRNA gene copies in this category are normalized to the volume (liter) of the sample.

4. SW for short path creek. The 16S rRNA gene copies in this category are normalized to the volume (liter) of the sample.

5. The 16S rRNA gene copies in this category are normalized to the wet weight (g) of the sample.

Supplementary Table S5. Genomic overview of metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) recovered from MLL02 and DL.

Classification of MAG using GTDB-tk	Total length of MAG (bp)	No. of scaffolds	GC content (%)	Completeness (%)	Contamination (%)	No. of predicted genes	No. of 16S rRNA gene
<i>Sulfuricurvum</i>	2,427,905	863	41.79	71.1	0	3087	1
<i>Thiobacillus</i>	3,275,533	700	61.67	72.87	0.32	3,793	0
<i>Hydrogenophaga</i>	3,047,584	210	68.77	95.14	0	2,974	0

Supplementary Table S6. Channel widths for low water periods near site CWL04 deduced from the SPOT imagery.

Date	River Width (m) Measurement Point 1	River Width (m) Measurement Point 2
2015/11/8	20.63	29.53
2016/4/6	20.40	38.35
2016/4/26	20.40	38.35
2016/5/9	21.63	41.62
2016/5/15	22.53	31.11
2016/12/9	23.24	37.21
2017/2/18	24.29	21.64
2017/4/18	25.04	19.10
2018/1/16	26.23	56.04
2018/3/27	20.13	26.87
2018/11/5	34.60	38.71
2019/2/28	16.05	28.45
2019/3/2	14.30	26.28
2019/3/27	22.66	31.15
2019/4/7	22.74	36.39
2019/4/25	21.53	30.77
2019/5/13	24.43	48.37
2019/11/10	23.37	22.33
2019/12/18	22.80	22.42
2020/1/14	22.83	25.92
2020/5/3	21.05	25.68
2020/11/27	27.58	37.21
2021/2/1	21.70	30.63
2021/5/22	22.17	31.76
2021/12/17	21.80	41.41
2022/1/16	21.59	42.78
2022/2/12	21.94	40.54
2022/4/18	27.63	51.27
2022/11/19	22.52	31.58
2022/12/3	21.89	28.54
2023/1/22	20.30	23.81
2023/3/23	24.70	34.07
2023/4/30	20.96	27.87
27.9 ± 8.5		

Supplementary Table S7. Flow velocities measured for low water periods near site CWL04.

Time period	Flow rate (m/s)
2018.01	1.3
2018.04	1.5
2018.05	1.0
2020.01	1.1
2020.03	1.0
2020.05	0.8
2022.01	1.4
2022.11	1.0
2023.06	0.9
	1.1 ± 0.2